

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20772656

Relationship Between Entry Qualification And Academic Performance Of National Diploma Students In Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship between entry qualification and National Diploma Students' academic performance in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research of correlational type to probe the opinions of the participants regarding relationship between entry qualification and academic performance among National Diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria. The study population consisted of 1,234 participants and a sample size of 291 was taken using Creswell (2012) table for determining sample size. The following two (2) researcher-designed rating scale to collect data from the participants was used which includes; Students Entry Qualification Rating Scale (SEQRS) and Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) to collect data. The questionnaire was structured on five-point Rating Scale (5) such as 5.0=Very High Extent (VHE), 4.0=High Extent (HE), 3.0=Moderate Extent (ME), 2.0=Low Extent (LE) and 1.0=Very Low Extent (VLE) respectively to measure the responses of the participants. The content validity of the Students Entry Qualification Rating Scale (SEQRS) and Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) were done by experts and academicians in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state, as well as, other experts in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto. The study conducted a trial testing of instrument using inter-Rater methods of reliability and the study obtained reliability index of 0.81 for Students Entry Qualification Rating Scale (SEQRS) and reliability index of 0.71 for Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) and this shows that the research instruments were found reliable for data collection. The study used descriptive statistics to answer research questions of the study, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software 20.0 version. The study found that WAEC, NECO and NABTEB as only entry qualification for the students to be admitted into National Diploma severely affect their academic performance, as many students have above the minimum requirements. Study concluded that, in addition to the basic entry requirements the management of the polytechnics can equally introduce internal examination for the prospective students to test integrity so as to genuinely select best among them. The study recommended that the polytechnic management through academic staff should continually assess and re-assess their students through rigorous academic engagement so as to enable them to acquire basic knowledge that would make them to stand the competitions in the labor market.

Keywords: Entry Qualifications, Academic Performance and Students.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria's education system, priority is being given to qualification to secure an admission for basic, post-basic, and tertiary education. To encourage enrolment into schools in recent years, especially admission into tertiary institutions, entry procedure is made flexible to allow a wider range of candidates to pursue their higher education. Although, predicting future performance from previous achievement is difficult, because many researchers have concluded that entry qualification do predict success or otherwise in high education. According to Anderson (2023) reported in their study that three and ninety (390) students were involved in a study from 2 basic nursing schools in Nigeria concluded that entry qualification does have a positive correlation to academic performance. Also, Alias and Zain (2016) compared the performance of the final year bachelor of Education degree students who entered the university from three different examination bodies in Nigeria which were: West African Examination council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). The results indicated that students' performances in SSCE strongly determined their academic success in tertiary institution.

Further, in a study conducted by Durotolu (2024) on the relationship between entry qualification and academic performance in undergraduate science courses at the university of Nairobi, Kenya, it was revealed that there was a significant positive correlation between entry qualification (Secondary School Certificate) and academic performance in Chemistry and Biology, even though is not the only variable that can predict performance. But the scenario seems different in the case of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. Students would have nine (9) credits in Senior Secondary School Certificate (WAEC, NECO or NABTEB), when given admission in the college, many of them get withdrawn in their first year. It is in view of the above background that this study deemed it necessary to investigate the relationship between student's entry qualification and academic performance in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto- Nigeria.

Statement Of The Problem

Educationists from different disciplines have always considered the background of the learners in the preparation of curricula and before every classroom instruction. The background of the learner is necessary for the formulation of educational objectives, which are what the learners are expected to achieve at the end of the course. The retention and completion of national diploma rate in Nigeria polytechnics are a global concern. The polytechnics in Nigeria are faced with the burden of increasing the number of graduating students while at the same time ensuring that new graduates are competent to function in the ever-changing labor market. The cut-throat competition in the labor market require that students who are graduating from the polytechnics must have strong background so as to enable them compete favorably. Retention and successful completion of National Diploma (ND) programme are complex issues that may involve a variety of academic and non-academic factors due to the fact that students from a diverse population group in terms of age and academic ability have been admitted. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) in collaboration with the management of the polytechnics in Nigeria has attempted to adopt a procedure for selecting entry requirements of students who are coming to enroll for the national diploma programmes so as reduce the level of failure. Inadequate preparation of these students as represented by their certificates in the senior school certificate resulted to their poor academic performance in the polytechnics. Many students have four credit and above as basic entry requirements but lack requisite knowledge buttress their WAEC, NECO NABTEB certificates. In the light of these, the study investigates how entry qualifications affect students' academic performance

Objectives Of The Study

The following objectives are to find out:

1. The extent of entry qualification among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria.

2. The level of academic performance among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria.
3. The relationship between entry qualification and academic performance among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions

1. What is the extent of entry qualification among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria?
2. What is the level of academic performance among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria.
3. What is the relationship between entry qualification and academic performance among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

Based on research questions and objectives, the study formulated and tested the following hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between entry qualification and academic performance among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is hinged on constructivism learning theory, constructivism, as a paradigm or worldview, posits that learning is an active, constructive process. The learner is an information constructor. People actively construct or create their own subjective representations of objective reality. New information is linked to prior knowledge, thus mental representations are subjective. Constructivism emphasizes the importance of the active involvement of learners in constructing knowledge for themselves (Dienye,2021). Students are thought to use background knowledge and concepts to assist them in their acquisition of novel information. When such new information is approached, the learner faces a loss of equilibrium with their previous understanding which demands a change in cognitive structure. This change effectively combines previous and novel information to form an improved cognitive schema. Constructivism can be both subjectively and contextually based. Under the theory of radical constructivism, understanding relies on one's subjective interpretation of experience as opposed to objective "reality". Similarly, idea of contextual constructivism encompasses the effects of culture and society on experience (Jimoh & Durotolu 2028). Constructivism asks why students do not learn deeply by listening to a teacher or reading from a textbook. To design effective teaching environments, it is believed that one needs a good understanding of what children already know when they come into the classroom. The curriculum should be designed in a way that builds on the pupil's background knowledge and is allowed to develop with them (Datti 2024). Begin with complex problems and teach basic skills while solving these problems (Kiisi2022). Constructivism has many varieties such as active learning, discovery learning, and knowledge building, but all versions promote a student's free exploration within a given framework or structure. The teacher acts as a facilitator who encourages students to discover principles for themselves and to construct knowledge by working answering open-ended questions and solving real-world problems. To do this, a teacher should encourage curiosity and discussion among his/her students as well as promoting their autonomy. In scientific areas in the classroom, constructivist teachers provide raw data and physical materials for the students to work with and analyze.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of studies have been carried out on the relationship between entry qualifications and academic performance of students. Some of the studies focused on the relationship between secondary certificate examination/general certificate examinations (SSCE/GCE) and their performance in corresponding subjects at Colleges of Education, Polytechnics and Universities. Others correlated the scores of candidates in UTME/JAMB or SSCE/GCE examination with their performance in the first year of

university education. Dienye (2021) for instance, correlated the performance of candidates JME and WASC aggregates in the same subjects with their performance in the preliminary year. He found that both JME and WASC correlated positively with performance in the preliminary year. However, he found that on the average, JME aggregate predicted success better (approximately 0.4) than WASC aggregate did (approximately 0.3). Similarly, Datti (2024) carried out a study on the predictive value of JME in selected school subjects. He sought to establish empirically, the predictive value of JME by correlating its scores with measures of first year university examination at the University Ollorin, in Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Geography and Economics. He discovered a significant correlation between JME and first year scores in Chemistry (0.72), Physics (0.59) and Economics (0.41) but low correlations in Geography (0.20) and Biology (0.52).

However, Kiisi (2022) in his study on the relationship between entry qualification and performance in A 'level chemistry: A case study of school of basic and remedial studies correlated between entry qualification and performance in A level chemistry at the school of Basic and remedial studies, Yobe State University, Damaturu. The grade in chemistry at the West African Examination Council (WAEC) or National Examination Council (NECO) is the predictor while the criterion is the grade earned in the short-structured test administered at the end of Basic 1. AS obtained from the profile of performances of the students, majority do not seem to have transferred what they have learnt in secondary school, in other words they do not exhibit previous knowledge. Perhaps they did not get the required experience while in school but possessed credit pass in chemistry at the final secondary school examination. Impact of gender on student performance is also revealed in this work. The findings here are in agreement with previous reports by Datti (2024) in contrast, there is only slight difference in the percentage credit passes between the two sexes in their SSCE/NECO entry qualification (85 and 87.5%). The findings from this study revealed that the set of students admitted for the program were generally not performing well and that the poor performance t more pronounced in the females. It also established that there is no correlation between the entry qualification and performance in 'A' level program. The findings stress the need for a renewed and concerted effort towards addressing the challenges of primary and secondary education in the state and the nation at large. Jimoh and Durotolu (2028) in their study, entry qualifications and academic performance of architecture students in building structures, they found that, except for the second semester of the second year of architecture studies, there exists no correlation between admission qualification and academic performance of students. However, female Students outperformed their male counterparts in all the semesters. They suggested the need for a more appropriate criteria for selecting prospective students into undergraduate architecture programmes in Nigerian universities. Such selection criteria should also attempt to match their aptitude with their attitude, the synergy of which will equip students to cope with the rigours of architectural study. Students need to develop the dexterity and analytical prowess needed for Building Structures.

The study of Alias and Zain (2016) relationship between senior secondary school certificate examination (SSCE) mathematics grades and final Nigeria certificate of education (NCE) mathematics students results of Niger state college of education Minna, showed a significant relationship between WASSCE entry grade in mathematics and the final NCE mathematics results. They recommended among others that State Ministry of Education should intensify more effort in conducting regular inspection of schools to ensure that effective teaching of mathematics is carried out in order to achieve the objectives of National Policy on Education which include the preparation of students for higher education (FRN, 2013). Based on the findings of their study, they concluded that the entry grades obtained by students in mathematics in WASSCE were significantly related to final NCE Mathematics result. However, this research also found out that there was no significant relationship between WASSCE entry grade and final NCE Mathematics result based on gender. They recommended among other things that, more emphasis should be given to the teaching of mathematics in secondary and primary schools by recruiting qualitative Mathematics teachers. In addition, faculties, departments and institutes of education in our universities as well as the colleges of education in Nigeria should include in their curriculum courses on the primary and secondary school mathematics curricula.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research of correlational type to probe the opinions of the participants regarding relationship between entry qualification and academic performance among national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria. The study population consisted of 1234 participants and a sample size of 291 was taken using Creswell (2012) table for determining sample size. The used the following two (2) researcher-designed rating scale to collect data from the participants which includes; Students Entry Qualification Rating Scale (SEQRS) and Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) to collect data. The questionnaire was structured on five-point Rating Scale (5) such as 5.0=Very High Extent (VHE), 4.0=High Extent (HE), 3.0=Moderate Extent (ME), 2.0=Low Extent (LE) and 1.0=Very Low Extent (VLE) respectively to measure the responses of the participants. The content validity of the Students Entry Qualification Rating Scale (SEQRS) and Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) were done by experts and academicians in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state, as well as, other experts in Usmanu Danfodiyo University. The study conducted a trial testing of instrument using inter-Rater methods of reliability and the study obtained reliability index of 0.81 for Students Entry Qualification Rating Scale (SEQRS) and reliability index of 0.71 for Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) and this shows that the research instruments were found reliable for data collection. The study used descriptive statistics to answer research questions of the study, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software 20.0 version.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between entry qualification and academic performance of national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested by subjecting the scores of entries qualification and that of academic performance of national diploma students to Pearson correlation analysis as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Relationship between entry qualification and academic performance of National Diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto State Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	R	Sig	Decision
Entry Qualification	291	20.23	3.16	355	0.457	0.001	H ₀₁
Academic Performance	291	19.56	1.50				Rejected

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 1 presented the results of descriptive statistics and correlation analysis for testing the students' entry qualification and academic performance has mean of 20.23 and standard deviation of 3.16 while academic performance has mean of 19.56 and standard deviation of 1.50. The result of the correlation analysis revealed the coefficient (*r*) of 0.457 with *p*-value=0.000<0.05. This result shows that there is strong, positive and significant students' entry qualification and academic performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis H₀₁ is rejected at 5% level of significance. This result revealed that there is significant relationship between entry qualification and academic performance of national diploma students in Umaru Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto state Nigeria This means that students' entry qualification has significant effect on students' academic performance.

Summary Of The Major Findings

Based on the results of the analysis, the following are the summary of the major findings

1. The study found that WAEC, NECO and NABTEB as only entry qualification for the students to be admitted into national diploma severely affect their academic performance, as many students have above the minimum requirements.
2. The study found that low academic performance of students in the polytechnics culminated to poor background in the secondary schools
3. The result also revealed that there is significant relationship between students' entry qualification and academic performance

CONCLUSION

Based on research findings this study concluded that, in addition to the basic entry requirements the management of the polytechnics can equally introduce internal examination for the prospective students to test integrity so as to genuinely select best among them. High performing prospective students can be targeted for the admission to ensure retention and subsequent successful completion of national diploma programmes

RECOMMENDATION

Based on findings and conclusions of this study, the following have been recommended; the polytechnic management through academic staff should continually assess and re-assess their students through rigorous academic engagement so as to enable them to acquire basic knowledge that would make them to stand the competitions in the labor market. The management should also, evaluate students' performance from time to time in order to remediate areas of laxity.

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